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Junctional activity at the cell membrane during transformation of the cervix resulting from high-risk HPV infection.

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We report here changes in gene expression indicative of a broader cell biologic event involving junctional activity at the cell membrane during oncogenesis by studying transformation in humans *in vivo* using the cervix following high-risk human papillomavirus (HPV) infection as a model.